

Scenario Planning for Sustainable Packaging

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1. Introduction

Sustainability is getting more and more important. To fulfil the needs of today, without endanger the needs of tomorrow is due to climate changes, the change of agriculture and limited resources more important than ever.

That has also an influence on companies across all industries, but to implement such sustainable oriented practices can be challenging.

Many enterprises are recognizing that there is a need to act more sustainably – but what is this all about?

There are three pillars of sustainability ¹:

- Social
- Economic
- Environmental

This paper is about developing a systemic approach for assessing the total material used during the lifecycle² of a of a packaged product from both the economic and the environmental perspective.

The final outcome is a set of metrics that compares different packaging options in order to support executives with deciding on the best option from an environmental and economic point of view.

Assessment of Packaging options

The packaging of an actual product does not only protect the product itself and hence reducing product loss due to damage, leakage, contamination, or spoiling (e.g. by exposure to oxygen or light).

It is also a key element for marketing the actual product by its physical appearance and providing information to the customer.

Plastics is a very important material for packaging as its properties can be designed to meet many requirements to protect the product (barrier, mechanical) and in can be given countless forms and appearances, from flexible to rigid packaging with prints and labels.

On the other hand, plastics have a big impact on the environment as it is produced mainly from fossil and non-renewable raw materials and is mostly not biodegradable if dumped as waste. Further the many different types of plastics as well as material combinations like laminates makes it difficult to recycle plastic packaging.

In March 2020, the European Plastic Pact was founded by 15 European Countries and 66 companies.

Amongst the goals are to reduce virgin plastic products and packaging by at least 20% (by weight) by 2025, with half of this reduction coming from an absolute reduction in plastics and Increase the use of recycled plastics in new products and packaging by 2025, with plastics using companies achieving an average of at least 30% recycled plastics (by weight) in their product and packaging range³.

Knowing and reducing total amount of plastic used in the lifecycle of a product is essential to reach those goals.

Similarly important is the assessment of alternate packaging options, different materials and designs as well as changes in the business model, e.g. moving from single use to re-use packaging.

Most current approaches fall short to give a holistic picture of the different options to choose.

The large number of different metrics increase ambiguity and make it difficult for executive to prioritize.

While the main focus is on environmental and sustainability aspects the financial side of different packaging options is mostly neglected.

Further most approaches show a snapshot of a steady state. The different parameters are being calculated for the estimated total volume of product being sold. Additionally data collection is often difficult and cumbersome and certain figures are being estimated.

Here an approach is presented that

- is based on actual data and current business plans
- puts different parameters (including financial numbers) next to each other
- shows the development of those figures over the whole lifecycle of the product
- compares those time series for different packaging options

2. The need for a systemic view over the product life cycle

Sustainability and financials are driven by many factors

Any change during the product lifecycle, supply chain and business model will influence the total amount material used for the product (i.e. both for the actual product and the packaging, respectively).

That in turn leads to different environmental impacts of the product packaging. Key Factors that influence the material consumption during the product lifecycle are for example:

- **Total time of the product lifecycle**, from product introduction to the exit.
The duration of the product being on the market determines the total volume being sold and hence the amount of material being used. When going for reusable packaging the time on the market influences the circulation number. It also has an effect on financial figures when using a discounted cash flow method or assessing options.
- **Production volumes** (and changes thereof) during the whole lifecycle
Those number affect the total need of material intake of the supply chain
- **Losses and waste along the whole supply chain**, including production, distribution and use.
Losses and waste mean that on the one hand more material is needed to deliver the amount of product requested by the customer. On the other hand, losses and waste mean unnecessary material use that is not being delivered to the customer but increase the environmental impact and costs.
Losses can be substantial losses especially in process chains. All cycles in circular economy are process chains with losses in each process.
- **Packaging design** (e.g. recycled material used, recyclability, types and amounts of materials used)
The use of recyclable materials and the ease for the customer to put packaging into the recycling process reduces environmental impact and waste.
- **Business model** (single use or re-use packaging)
Usually single use packaging needs less material as it does not need to resist as much mechanical stress as re-use packaging, hence production needs less energy, material and financial resources. Although re-use packaging needs more resources for production the lower amount of resources needed for logistics, cleaning etc can be an advantage in the long run.
- Recycling and re-use rates influence waste rates
- **Export rates** have an impact on the amount of packaging available if re-use packaging is used. Packaging from exported product is not likely to return to the supply chain and can be considered as process loss.

- **Lead times** throughout the value chain have an impact on the total material that is being used. The longer the lead time the more material is in the process to fulfil the throughput necessary to meet customer demand ⁴.

Any useful combination leads to a business scenario that not only determines the environmental impact that can be expressed in several indicators as carbon footprint, acidification, eutrophication, and others.

Each scenario also represents a different financial business case. That's why the whole supply chain needs to be assessed over the whole product lifecycle in order to get a comprehensive assessment of different options.

Availability of data and data quality

Collecting waste figures can be very cumbersome and prone to error.

The author's experience from numerous process optimization projects is that waste figures are not completely available in ERP systems. Initiatives to collect waste figures from processes and supply chains manually are difficult, time consuming, prone to error and only reflect a single snapshot.

Further the collected waste figures can explain a part of the difference between material input and product output.

This slows down many analyses and makes the results less reliable.

Other key figures like the circulation number of re-use packaging are often being estimated.

When assessing the impact of re-use packaging any change in the circulation number leads to a big change in the results.

Wrong estimations can lead to results that don't reflect reality correctly.

Ambiguity makes decision making difficult

While policy makers need to decide on guidelines for countries and industries to follow many important decisions in the industries need to be made by executives managers of producing companies.

Changes in policies and sustainability goals need to be reflected in business strategies and can have major impacts on investments in future technologies.

From an academic standpoint it is understandable that a range of sophisticated metrics need to be developed to cover the whole impact on the environment. Processing different materials lead to different emissions that cause different damage to different ecosystems.

As a result a whole range of different indicators can be defined to quantify environmental impact⁵.

From the change management point of view this can slow down and even inhibit effective decisions.

Slowing down the decision process by increasing sophistication

The more sophisticated and detailed metrics as methods become the more time and effort can be put into analyzing more and more aspects. That can lead to “paralysis by analysis”⁶ where developing, measuring and calculating the indicators becomes a mean to itself instead of being a means for the purpose of supporting decisions for the best business case.

Increasing ambiguity due to information overflow

With a growing number of indicators descriptions of scenarios become more ambiguous.

Leaders (politicians and managers in the industry) often have a hard time to prioritize the metrics in order to make the best decisions.

What about single-use items and the massive amount of waste and the pollutant to the environment? How about the costs in the value chain? Furthermore, how will the consumers react? Is it cheaper to choose a plastic free status?

Prioritization helps decision making

To support meaningful decisions all the information regarding different aspects of the packaging solution need to be prioritized.

Several means to do this can be proposed.

Hierarchy of approaches to reduce waste

One way to set priorities is using the waste hierarchy⁷ that shows the reduction of waste in the most preferable way (see Figure 1).

To reuse a material is more effective than recycling it. The goal should therefore be to use a system that reuses packaging materials more often.

On top of that the whole supply chain should be optimized to reduce or even avoid material use throughout the lifecycle of the product.

Figure 1: : Waste Hierarchy, data from Committee for Waste Reduction ⁷

Circular Economy

Most of the current approaches in Circular Economy focus on the following three principles⁸ (see Figure 2):

- Design out waste and pollution
- Keep products and materials in use
- Regenerate natural systems

The aim to design out waste is to design a product or packaging in a way that waste is the input for another step.

Another approach is to prolong product life span by better design and reconditioning product.

So most approaches in Circular Economy address the levels of recover, recycle and reuse in the waste hierarchy by closing cycles, increase recyclability by better product/packaging design, using re-use products and packaging or recover waste to reintroducing the material into the production process.

Approaches to reach the level of reduce/avoid mostly deal with packaging design where the amount of material used is being reduced.

OUTLINE OF A CIRCULAR ECONOMY

PRINCIPLE

1

Preserve and enhance natural capital by controlling finite stocks and balancing renewable resource flows
ReSOLVE levers: regenerate, virtualise, exchange

Renewables Finite materials

Regenerate Substitute materials Virtualise Restore

Renewables flow management

Stock management

PRINCIPLE

2

Optimise resource yields by circulating products, components and materials in use at the highest utility at all times in both technical and biological cycles
ReSOLVE levers: regenerate, share, optimise, loop

PRINCIPLE

3

Foster system effectiveness by revealing and designing out negative externalities
All ReSOLVE levers

Minimise systematic leakage and negative externalities

1. Hunting and fishing
2. Can take both post-harvest and post-consumer waste as an input
Source: Ellen MacArthur Foundation, SUN, and McKinsey Center for Business and Environment; Drawing from Braungart & McDonough, Cradle to Cradle (C2C).

Figure 2: The outline of a circular economy showing closing different loops to keep material and resources in the system.[8]

Lean Management and Circular Economy

Lean is the western adaptation of the principles of the Toyota Production System (TPS)⁹.

One key part of the TPS is Just in Time Production that aims to make only “what is needed, when it is needed, and in the amount needed” and Producing quality products efficiently through the complete elimination of waste and inconsistencies.

Lean principles can be applied to production processes as well as administrative processes and whole supply chains.

A combined approach of Lean with Circular Economy where process chains also form loops can help to consistently reach the ultimate level in the waste hierarchy – reducing and avoiding waste in the whole supply chain.

Hierarchy of metrics – including financials

Although Sustainability and Social Responsibility are playing more and more important parts in management, business decisions are still heavily following the Friedman doctrine¹⁰ that the main goal is to increase the profitability of the business.

Further most incentives for executives are based on financial results of the company such as total shareholder returns¹¹

That means to support meaningful decisions that change actual products and packaging, executives need to have a structured view of different options that also shows the financial impact of each option.

Snapshots of steady states don't give the whole picture

Most approaches to Life Cycle Assessment and Material flow analysis only show a steady state picture.

Analysing different scenarios shows that depending on the lifecycle stage and the sales volumes of the product different indicators for sustainability, material usage or costs behave differently in relation to each other.

That means that a certain packaging option would be preferable in one scenario (e.g. low sales volumes, short time on the market) while being less preferable in other scenarios.

As those circumstances on the market can change over the lifecycle executive decisions can be better supported by showing when which option is preferable.

3. Simulating Business Cases

For building business cases that cover the lifecycle of the product two major areas need to be analysed.

1. The actual processes in the supply chain
2. The business plan with anticipated sales volumes over the whole lifecycle

Analysing the supply chain

As shown in Figure 3, when looking at processes, process chains and supply chains from a Lean Management perspective the focus lies on the flow of material, especially

- Inflows
- Outflows
- Waste
- Loss
- Throughputs

- Lead times

Figure 3: Hypothetical example of a supply chain with circular loops, inflows, waste and losses. The thickness of the flows represents the throughput per time, the length represents the lead time of the respective process

Process Steps in the Supply Chain

As a first step all the relevant steps of the supply chain need to be listed. This can be the whole system as shown in Figure 3: Hypothetical example of a supply chain with circular loops, inflows, waste and losses. The thickness of the flows represents the throughput per time, the length represents the lead time of the respective process, or it can be just the part within the systems boundary of the company.

However, the full view on environmental and financial impact can only be seen if the whole system is being covered.

- Examples are
- Production
- Filling
- Distribution (incl. Sales)
- Use (by the customer)
- Recycling/Re-use

It is important to do this on a rather high level. Choosing a too detailed level can lead to many inflows and outflows to be covered which in turn slows down the process and adds complexity that does not add any value.

Process Metrics

The next step is to gather the following information for each of those processes

- Inflow (which is the outflow from the previous process)

- Outflow (which is the inflow of the next process)
- Recycling rates or volumes
- Export rates at the Distribution step
- Throughput (e.g. per month)
- Lead time of the process (from inflow to outflow)

Those numbers are easily available in any ERP system or can very easily be collected on the shop floor or on site.

The only figures that can only be estimated (e.g. by using numbers from respective studies) are those for the “Use” step at the customer/consumer.

Those figures are:

- How long does the customer possess the product (from purchase until the packaging is being disposed or put into the recycle or re-use process)?
- What amount of packaging is being kept by the customer, disposed or returned into recycling/re-use?

Another key figure is the sales volume (e.g. for a representative month) as this drives the amount of material needed from upstream processes and the amount of material provided to downstream processes as recycling or re-use.

Calculations

Starting with the Sales number several figures can be calculated:

- Waste
- WIP (Work in Process)
- WIP Factor
- Supply Chain Yield

Losses

Waste is all the material that has been used in the process but is not part of the output that is delivered to the next step.

Below are calculations for two examples.

Distribution process

$$Ld = D - S - Rd$$

With:

Ld ... Loss in distribution

D ... distributed volume

Sp ... Sold packaging units

Rd ... Recycled packaging units during distribution

This approach calculates the total waste of the process

The waste of the production step can be calculated as:

$$Lp = Iv + Ir - F - Rp$$

With:

Lp ... Loss in production

Iv ... Virgin material input

Ir ... Recycled material input

F ... filled volume

Rp ... Recycled waste during production

WIP (Work in Process = Inventory)

This figure shows how much material is present in the process at a given throughput rate (e.g sold or produced units in a certain time).

Inventory can be influenced by higher throughput and by longer lead times (material on stock, transport, waiting times etc).

Based on Little's Law⁴ this can be calculated for the distribution process as

$$WIPd = Sd \times LTd$$

With:

WIPd ... Inventory of the distribution process

Spd ... Sold packing units per day

LTd ... Lead time of distribution in days (from delivery to the point of sales till purchasing by the customer)

WIP Factor

This number calculates how many units of packaging are present in the system for a certain throughput in Sales.

The WIP Factor is important to calculate the number of packaging units needed in a system with re-use packaging.

$$WIPFactor = \frac{\sum WIPp + WIPf + WIPd + WIPc + WIPr}{Sp}$$

With:

WIPp ... Inventory of the production process

WIPf ... Inventory of the filling process

WIPd ... Inventory of the distribution process

WIPc ... Inventory at the customer

WIPr ... Inventory of the recycling or re-use process

Sp ... monthly number of packaging units sold

Supply Chain Yield

The total yield of the supply chain is a key indicator for the material efficiency of the supply chain or parts thereof.

As an example in the ideal case with a circular process that uses recycled/re-used material for the production of packaging this indicator can be calculated as follows:

$$Y_{sc} = \frac{I_r}{I_r + I_v}$$

With:

Iv ... Virgin material input

Ir ... Recycled material input

It can also be calculated for a part of the supply chain, for example from production to purchase of good product:

$$Y_{sc} = \frac{S_p}{I_r + I_v}$$

With:

Ir ... Recycled material input

Iv ... Virgin material input

Sp ... Number of packaging units sold

Screenshots of a Calculation Tool can be seen in

Simulating Business Cases

The next step is building the business cases, deriving indicators and plotting them over the time of the product lifecycle.

Data needed

Following information is needed

- Projected monthly sales figures of the product (according to marketing plans)
Here also different scenarios can be calculated, including
 - Ramp up during introduction
 - Phase out before exit
 - Seasonalities
 - Marketing initiatives

- Units of packaging per unit of product (e.g. 3 bottles with 0,33 litres for 1 litre of beer, one cardboard box for 12 pieces of product, etc.)
- Amount of each material in one unit of packaging
- Costs of each unit of packaging
- CAPEX and OPEX costs (Investments, depreciation and additional costs) and time of payment
- Monthly capital costs of the company (e.g. WACC)
- Sustainability indicators (e.g. carbon footprint, acidification, etc.) for
 - Production of each packaging material
 - Transport of packaging
 - Sorting, cleaning & recycling

Calculations

The following indicators can be calculated (per month)

- Units of packaging sold
- Circulation number
- Amount of material(s) for packaging (single and cumulated)
- Costs of packaging
- Total costs (including CAPEX and OPEX)
- Sustainability indicators

Units of packaging sold

The number of packaging units is the key figure for all other calculations.

It is calculated as follows:

$$Sp = S \times Pp$$

With:

Sp ... Units of packaging sold

S ... Volume of product sold

Pp ... Number of packaging units per unit of product

This number is then calculated for each month of the business plan containing the planned volume of product across the whole lifecycle.

Units of packaging needed

This is where the WIP-Factor comes into play.

For each unit of packaging sold the system needs to contain more units of packaging as there will be units in the re-use cycle.

For constant sales numbers from one month to the other the same number of packaging units will be circulating in the system. Additional units of packaging will

only be necessary to replace the loss in the supply chain and if sales numbers increase.

So, for re-use packaging the calculation is as follows:

$$Pr = (Spc - Spp + Lf + Ld + Lc + Lr) \times WIPFactor$$

With:

Pr ... Units of re-use packaging needed
Spc ... Units of packaging sold in the respective month
Spp ... Units of packaging sold in the previous month
Lf ... Loss during the filling step
Ld ... Loss during the distribution step
Lc ... Loss due to the customer
Lr ... Loss in the recycling process
WIPFactor ... WIP Factor as calculated above

With single-use packaging one unit of packaging is needed for each unit being sold.

This number is calculated for each month over the lifecycle of the product.

$$Ps = Spc$$

With:

Ps ... Units of single-use packaging needed
Spc ... Units of packaging sold in the respective month

This number needs to be calculated for each month of the product lifecycle.

This number will be cumulated over time for single-use packaging as new packaging is needed for each sold unit.

Time series

Taking all monthly figures, the number of packaging units per month can be plotted over time.

Because the total impact of the packaging option is the main point not the single figures per month are being used.

For single-use packaging each new sold unit of product needs a new unit of packaging.

That's why the numbers need to be culminated over the months.

Units of re-use packaging circulate in the system and are being used several times. New units of packaging are only added to replace lost units (damage, loss, waste) and if the number of sold units is growing.

Here the value of Pr is being used for each respective month.

An example with comparisons of three different packaging options (glass bottles) can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Time series for the number of packaging units over the lifecycle of the product. The comparison is between three different options of glass bottles: 0,3 litre single use, 0,3 litre re-use and 0,5 litre re-use bottles.

It can be seen that the number of single use packaging units is increasing with each unit being sold.

In contrast the number of re-use packaging units grows faster in the ramp-up phase to fill up the system. Once that has been reached only a slight increase happens to replace losses.

In the long run in this case much less units of packaging would be needed over the lifecycle of the product when re-use packaging would be used.

Packaging costs

Using the numbers in the time series the development of the costs for purchasing the packaging can be calculated.

For single use the costs are calculated as follows:

$$Cs = Spc \times (Cts + Csr)$$

With:

Cs ... Costs of single use packaging

Spc ... Units of packaging sold in the respective month

Cts ... Costs of transport of single use packaging in the respective month

Csr ... Costs of recycling of material from single use packaging in the respective

month

$$Cr = (Spc - Spp + Lf + Ld + Lc + Lr) \times (Ctr + Crr)$$

With:

Cr ... Costs of re-use packaging

Spc ... Units of packaging sold in the respective month

Spp ... Units of packaging sold in the previous month

Lf ... Loss during the filling step

Ld ... Loss during the distribution step

Lc ... Loss due to the customer

Lr ... Loss in the recycling process

Ctr ... Costs of transport of re-use packaging in the respective month

Crr ... Costs of recycling of re-use packaging in the respective month

For the same example the costs would develop as shown in Figure 5

Figure 5: Packaging costs for 3 bottles.

In this example the re-use options become more feasible compared to the single use option after 1 and 2 years, respectively.

Discounted Cashflow

Sound financial appraisal is crucial for making decisions. From a financial any scenario is an investment case. That is why this aspect is evaluated by applying the discounted cash flow method (DCF).

In the first step additional costs added to each month where they will occur

- OPEX
- CAPEX and depreciation
- One-off payments

Then those costs are discounted using the monthly capital costs of the company.

For the example used the comparison of the DCFs of the three packaging options are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Discounted Cash flow for three packaging options. In this case an additional washing machine had to be purchased and the depreciation is added monthly. In addition, crates had to be purchased.

In the example shown the additional investments in a washing machine and crates leads to the case that 0,33 litre single use bottles are financially more feasible than 0,33 litre re-use bottles in the first 2 years, whereas 0,5 litre re-use bottles become the most feasible option in less than one year.

Sustainability Indicators

Similar as with the costs of packaging, using the numbers in the time series it can be calculated how different sustainability indicators (like CO₂ footprint, Acidification etc) develop over time.

As the calculation are similar for any of those indicators it is only shown in a general manner

For single use the costs are calculated as follows:

$$Iss = Spc \times (Ists + Isrs)$$

With:

Iss ... Sustainability indicator of single use packaging

Spc ... Units of packaging sold in the respective month

Ists ... Sustainability indicator for transport of material from one piece of single use packaging in the respective month

Isrs ... Sustainability indicator for recycling of material from one piece of single use packaging in the respective month

The calculation for re-use packaging is as follows:

$$Isr = (Spc - Spp + Lf + Ld + Lc + Lr) \times (Ctr + Crr)$$

With:

Isr ... Costs of re-use packaging

Spc ... Units of packaging sold in the respective month

Spp ... Units of packaging sold in the previous month

Lf ... Loss during the filling step

Ld ... Loss during the distribution step

Lc ... Loss due to the customer

Lr ... Loss in the recycling process

Istr ... Costs of transport of re-use packaging in the respective month

Isrr ... Costs of recycling of re- use packaging in the respective month

For the same example the CO₂ footprint develops is shown in

Figure 7: The time series for the CO₂ footprint for the 3 filling options.

This graph shows that single use packaging builds up CO₂ equivalents over time whereas re-use packaging quickly build up CO₂ equivalents until the system is filled. After that, the increase is slower because only effects of transport and re-use (washing etc) are added.

This calculation can be repeated for every other indicator for sustainability.

Material Consumption

Especially for plastics the total material consumption is an important information.

If the aim is to reach the goals of the European Plastic Pact (20% reduction of virgin plastics by 2025) calculating the total amount of virgin plastics used is a crucial information.

Using the numbers in the time series the consumption of any material over time can be calculated.

For single use the costs are calculated as follows:

$$Ms = Spc \times Msp$$

With:

Ms ... Total mass of a certain material used for single use packaging

Spc ... Units of packaging sold in the respective month

Msp ... Mass of the material used for each single unit of single use packaging

$$Mr = (Spc - Spp + Lf + Ld + Lc + Lr) \times Mrp$$

With:

Mr ... Total mass of a certain material used for single use packaging

Spc ... Units of packaging sold in the respective month

Spp ... Units of packaging sold in the previous month

Lf ... Loss during the filling step

Ld ... Loss during the distribution step

Lc ... Loss due to the customer

Lr ... Loss in the recycling process

Mrp ... Mass of the material used for each single unit of re-use packaging

The material consumption for the example with the bottles develop as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Development of the consumption of glass for single use and re-use options.

In this example the consumption of glass for single use bottles exceeds the numbers for re-use bottles after the first year. After that re-use bottles are favourable.

Circulation number

Instead of estimating this number (how often will one unit of packaging being re-used) it can be calculated based on the actual processes and the marketing plan, i.e. projected sales.

This calculated number is closer to the real number than estimations.

The calculation for single use packaging is the total number of packaging units sold over the lifecycle.

$$CN_s = \frac{\sum Spc}{\sum Ps} = 1$$

With:

CNs ... Circulation number for single use packaging

$\sum Spc$... Total number of packaging units sold by the end of the lifecycle

$\sum Ps$... Total number of packaging units used by the end of the lifecycle

For re-use packaging the maximum value for P is being used:

$$CNr = \frac{\sum Spc}{max. Pr}$$

With:

CNr ... Circulation number for re-use packaging

$\sum Spc$... Total number of packaging units sold by the end of the lifecycle

max. Pr ... the maximum value of re-use packaging needed from all months

It is also possible to plot the development of the circulation number over time.

The circulation number for single use packaging stays at 1.

For re-use packaging the monthly value of the Circulation Number can be calculated as follows

$$CNrm = \sum_{i=1}^n Spc / Pr$$

With:

CNrm ... Circulation number for re-use packaging for each month

Spc ... Number of packaging units sold for each month

Pr ... Number of re-use packaging units in the system in the respective month

For our example with the three options for bottles the circulation number develops over time as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Development of the circulation numbers for single use and re-use bottles

In this case it is obvious that just estimating the Circulation number for assessing sustainability of re-use packaging can be risky.

Choosing too high values can lead to over-optimistic evaluations of environmental impact and choosing too low values would lead to worse number than is the case.

4. Possible applications

This method for be used to answer several different scenarios.

- Changing customer demand
Changing sales volumes due to different reasons like seasonality, marketing campaigns, etc.
- Sensitivity Analysis
Different parameters regarding changes in markets, customer behaviour, process performance, prices, marketing strategies can be tested form impact on sustainability and economic outcome.
- Comparing different packaging solutions
Their supply chains differ, including losses and recycling rates
- Changing customer behaviour
small design changes or campaigns can increase or decrease the rates of littering or recycling
- Changes in the supply chain
Reducing losses and shortening lead times can reduce the total amount of packaging needed and reduce the total environmental impact of the product
- Changes in the cost structure
If costs of goods and services change or new investments need to be made the financial impact can be assessed
- Realistic circulation numbers
If circulation numbers are only estimated the calculation of sustainability indicators for re-use packaging can be off.
In a personal communication an executive of a major Austrian brewery has confirmed that Sustainability experts proposed estimated circulation numbers for re-use bottles that were much higher than the numbers that had been calculated using sales and warehouse data.
Estimations can be checked by using this model to support better evaluations ins future.

Further Circulation Numbers based on real supply chain data and business plans can help to agree on more realistic prices. Many retailers get billed a

certain cost for each unit of re-use packaging. At the end of the each business period those prices are re-negotiated based on annually calculated circulation numbers [personal Communication with a major Austrian retailer).

The risk of calculating Circulation numbers for each year is that many re-use packaging can be used for longer than a year. Annual assessments can lead to Circulation Number that are too high which means that the retailer could pay a price that is too high.

Using realistic Circulation Numbers over the whole lifecycle of the product would be a more reliable basis for negotiating prices for re-use packaging.

5. Further Outlook

This paper shows how sustainability of packaging solutions can be assessed in novel ways to reflect more important aspects like the development of indicators over the whole lifecycle, the total amount of material used over the whole life of the product and the financial impact of changes in packaging design materials and supply chain.

The target audience are executives who need to decide on more strategic topics like (also long term) investments in new equipment, new products, changes in packaging and similar.

With increasing focus on sustainability by the EU and local governments decisions that make real impact get more important.

The approach presented in this paper aims to support business leaders to make better decisions by providing relevant information that is closer to the reality of the business..

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